

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842

ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

MULTIDISCIPLINARY E-PUBLICATION

Vol. IV Issue X, October 2024

Monthly Issue

International Circulation

Pinagpala

PUBLISHING SERVICES

NBDB Reg. No. 3269

DTI Business Reg. No. 3034433

TIN 293-150-678 / Business Permit No. 8183

San Vicente, Tarlac City, Philippines, 2300

pinagpalapublishingservices@gmail.com

+639985799958

*"Write. Connect.
Educate."*

@pinagpalapublishing

pinagpala_publishing

www.pinagpalapublishing.com

School infrastructure: Matters to school performance

Adonis A. Cara, MAEd

Teacher III

*Sto. Rosario National High School- Sto. Domingo
Nueva Ecija, Region III*

The infrastructure of a school plays a critical role in shaping students' learning experiences, overall academic performance, and well-being. School infrastructure serves as the foundation upon which educational outcomes are built. The physical environment, resources, and facilities available in a school significantly impact student engagement, academic achievement, and overall school performance. Several key factors highlight the importance of school infrastructure in contributing to school performance:

1. **Physical Environment:** A well-maintained and conducive physical environment is essential for creating a positive learning atmosphere. Schools with adequate classrooms, libraries, laboratories, and recreational spaces provide students with the necessary facilities to engage in effective learning activities. A safe, clean, and comfortable physical environment can enhance students' focus, motivation, and overall well-being, ultimately influencing their academic performance. A well-designed and functional school environment can enhance student motivation and focus.

2. **Technology and Resources:** Access to modern technology, up-to-date resources, and educational materials is crucial for supporting teaching and learning processes. Schools equipped with computers, internet connectivity, educational software, and other technological tools offer students opportunities to engage in interactive learning, research, and collaboration. Adequate resources enable teachers to design innovative lessons, tailor instruction to individual student needs, and facilitate a more engaging and effective learning experience.

3. **Safety and Security:** School infrastructure that prioritizes safety and security creates a conducive environment for learning. Proper safety measures, such as secure building structures, emergency response protocols, and surveillance systems, help ensure the physical well-being of students and staff. A safe and secure school environment fosters a sense of trust, comfort, and stability, which are essential for students to focus on their academic pursuits and succeed in their learning endeavors.

4. **Comfort and Health:** School infrastructure that promotes physical comfort and supports students' health and well-being can have a positive impact on academic performance. Facilities with proper ventilation, heating, and lighting contribute to a comfortable learning environment that enhances students' concentration and overall mood. Additionally, access to nutritious meals, clean water, and appropriate health services within the school premises can improve students' physical health, attendance rates, and academic outcomes.

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

World Education Connect Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue X (October 2024), p.192-197, International
ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X
Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com
Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services
DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183
National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

5. Community Engagement: School infrastructure can also serve as a hub for community engagement and collaboration. Schools that offer multipurpose spaces for community events, parent-teacher meetings, and extracurricular activities foster strong connections between school, families, and the wider community. Such community engagement initiatives create a supportive and inclusive school culture, strengthen relationships among stakeholders, and contribute to a positive school climate that enhances student performance and overall well-being.

In essence, school infrastructure plays a vital role in shaping the learning environment, resources available to students, and overall culture of a school, all of which contribute to student engagement, academic success, and school performance. By investing in high-quality facilities, technology, safety measures, health resources, and community partnerships, schools can create an environment that nurtures academic success, fosters student growth, and promotes a culture of learning excellence. Prioritizing school infrastructure as a key component of education ensures that students have the resources, support, and opportunities they need to thrive, succeed, and reach their full potential.

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.13995816

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

EFFECTIVENESS OF SCIENCE INTERACTIVE LEARNING AND INTERVENTION PROGRAM

AMOR C. HABILING

Teacher III

Piilla National High School, SDO Rizal

Introduction

Science Education aims to develop scientific literacy and understanding of basic concepts among learners. However, declining performance in science subjects is linked to factors such as inadequate laboratory facilities, modern technology teaching, and students' lack of interest. Science is perceived as abstract, making it difficult for students to understand. The Education Act of 1982 mandates competent instruction and accountability for students' development. School administrators and teachers must ensure equity by identifying student needs and providing extensive knowledge. Teachers should constantly innovate their instruction and choose appropriate materials and strategies to improve student achievement. Intervention programs can alleviate factors contributing to student performance and increase curiosity and interest in the subject.

The Science Interactive Learning and Intervention Program (SILIP) is a constructivist learning approach that encourages students to engage in activities that stimulate curiosity and experiential learning. It uses strategies like whole class discussions, group work, and peer tutoring, and emphasizes the role of Science teachers.

Method

The researcher used a descriptive-experimental method to study the factors affecting the performance of Grade 8 students in Piilla National High School's Science program. The study involved purposive sampling and item analysis of the first quarter examination. The study focused

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

World Education Connect Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue X (October 2024), p.192-197, International
ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X
Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com
Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services
DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183
National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

on students with grades below 75 and identified struggling students. A proposal and action plan were submitted to the principal, and orientation was conducted with parents and students. The program was implemented with the cooperation of Grade 8 Science teachers. The study used mean and T-test for dependent sample to determine the impact of the program on student performance.

Results and Discussion

The study reveals that grade 8 students' performance before and after the implementation of the Science Interactive Learning and Intervention Program (SILIP) was significantly improved. Pretest results showed a higher performance in Science topics, while post-test results showed a higher performance. The calculated T-value, which is less than the significance level of 0.05, rejects the null hypothesis.

Conclusion

The Science Interactive Learning and Intervention Program (SILIP) significantly improved the performance of Grade 8 students, resulting in increased test scores. The program's interactive approach, including hands-on activities and personalized learning experiences, made science more accessible and interesting, retaining students' attention and deepening their comprehension. The success of SILIP highlights the importance of targeted intervention programs in addressing educational challenges and demonstrating that with the right tools, learning barriers can be overcome and academic outcomes can be enhanced.

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.13985125

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

World Education Connect Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue X (October 2024), p.192-197, International

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

IMPLEMENTATION OF PROJECT IMPACT: EXPLORING ITS SUCCESS AND CHALLENGES DURING AND AFTER THE PANDEMIC

AMOR C. HABILING

Teacher III

Piilla National High School, SDO Rizal

The integration of computers in the educational system in the Philippines is gaining momentum, with robots becoming more prevalent worldwide. Project IMPACT (Introduction to Arduino and Mobile Application Development for Students and Teachers) focused on computer programming, robotics, and mobile app creation to encourage students to enhance their skills in Robotics and Automation. Launched in 2019-2020, the program was implemented for three consecutive years at Piilla National High School during the pandemic.

Despite challenges such as limited resources and sudden changes in class schedules, the project team adapted and adapted to the new normal setup. The school participated in a virtual robotics competition this year, showcasing the tangible outcomes of their learning and potential impact on their future careers.

The opening of classes is considered as the most challenging part of school year 2020 – 2021 not only for the Project team but for the entire education sector. COVID-19 had brought sudden changes on the timetable of the various activities connected to meeting the target objectives. However, the continuous brainstorming and exchange of ideas led the team to come up with different strategies and started adapting the new normal setup, leveraging technology as an advantage for the project's implementation. Moreover, this year marked the school's first participation in a virtual robotics competition, which served as a test of the project's effectiveness. The project team initiated a proactive approach by inviting stakeholders and submitting a detailed proposal to the division office, securing additional resources and support. This strategic move not only outlined the project's achievements and future goals but also fostered a sense of ownership and collaboration, ensuring the project's continued success and benefiting more students and reinforcing STEM education's importance in the learning community.

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

World Education Connect Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue X (October 2024), p.192-197, International

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

The success of Project led to the launch of Project UPGRADE, a robotics training initiative aimed at expanding its reach and impact. The initiative aims to make training more accessible and inclusive, inspiring more students to pursue robotics and STEM fields. It also emphasizes community involvement, partnering with local businesses, educational institutions, and community leaders for resources, mentorship, and advocacy.

Despite the promising start, Project UPGRADE faces several challenges that need to be addressed to achieve its full potential. One significant gap is the insufficient number of robotics kits available for training. To overcome this, the project team is actively seeking additional funding and donations to purchase more kits and exploring cost-effective alternatives and innovative solutions. Another critical area that requires attention is the lack of a comprehensive robotics curriculum. It ensures that students acquire the necessary knowledge and skills at each stage of their training. The project team is currently working on developing a curriculum that aligns with educational standards and industry requirements. They are collaborating with educators, robotics experts, and curriculum developers to create a robust framework that covers fundamental concepts, advanced techniques, and real-world applications.

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.13985133

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessed M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.